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Short Summary of results
<p>This report summarises a series of model simulations conducted with the E3ME model, analysing the macroeconomic implications of LMT uptake scenarios in a number of national case studies: Switzerland, Sweden, Netherlands, Canada and Germany. The report outlines the process of development of scenario narratives and inputs, scenario design, and model results for each of the selected.</p> <p>The LMT scenarios developed in this deliverable will feed into the development of global LMT scenarios, which are also to be modelled with E3ME in the D7.5 deliverable.</p>
Evidence of accomplishment
This report.

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g. climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Executive summary

IPCC scenarios that aim to hold the global temperature to acceptable values rely on the large-scale implementation and success of a range of techniques and practices. One area is land-based climate mitigation techniques and practices (LMTs), which is a main focus for carbon sequestration (IPCC, 2022). To understand the realistic potential of LMTs, we first need to assess the risks related to implementation barriers as well as the potential impacts of LMTs.

This deliverable addresses this need by providing modelling analysis of the macroeconomic impacts of LMT adoption using the E3ME model. Whereas the feasibility of an LMT's adoption in a given national context is mainly assessed through qualitative assessments of stakeholders, alongside the development of a credible business case to ensure sustainability of the LMT at the microeconomic and community level, the political feasibility and sustainability of LMT implementation rests on an understanding of the significant impacts that scaling up these LMTs to a national level could for the national economy.

Scaling up LMTs in this way can have significant impacts on the agriculture and forestry sectors, with implications for employment, prices of agricultural outputs, and economic output itself. Furthermore, competition for land means that scaling up LMTs implies a reduction in land available for non-LMT land uses, some of which may be of significant economic importance, depending on the context. These economic impacts may be considered as trade-offs with the potential environmental benefits of LMT adoption. Equally, LMT adoption may lead to macroeconomic benefits, including such as net gains in employment or economic output. Modelling of LMT scenarios using a comprehensive macroeconomic model such as E3ME can reveal under which conditions LMT adoption may be beneficial or detrimental to the economy as a whole.

In this report, we analyse adoption of LMT portfolios at the national scale in five case study countries: Switzerland, Sweden, the Netherlands, Canada, and Germany. In cooperation with stakeholders, we developed quantified assumptions scenarios regarding the uptake of each LMT within each national portfolio. These quantified assumptions were then entered as inputs into an E3ME modelling scenario, and the results from these scenario model runs were analysed to draw policy conclusions from the macroeconomic perspective.

The case studies analysed were diverse not only in the portfolio of LMTs selected for each country, but also in terms of the diversity of scenario elements taken into consideration, and local economic contextual details which affected assumptions. For example, some scenarios included a business case for the LMT portfolio, notably including carbon credits, but also including the sale of products linked to the LMT (such as wood products from forestry), while others did not consider the question of revenues or compensation for LMT managers. For carbon credits, different funding mechanisms were considered, including a public carbon credit system funded through either taxpayer contributions or borrowing. Some LMTs considered the impact of upscaling the LMT portfolio on alternative, competing land uses and associated economic activity: for instance, the Netherlands case

study considered the impact of adopting various LMTs on the existing, nationally significant agricultural sector.

With such a diversity of case studies, it is difficult to draw any overarching conclusions. However, one recurring theme is that the economic impacts of land uses and economic activity displaced by upscaling LMTs can in many cases be much more significant than the economic impacts of the LMT activity itself. To a large extent these indirect impacts depend on the local context, and on what kind of economic activity is being displaced. In some cases, these sectoral shifts could be a source of political contestation between the winners and losers of LMT adoption. Another consideration is the business case of the LMT itself, and what are its sources of revenue. Whether LMTs are funded through taxpayer-funded government carbon credits, or borrowing-funded, can have a significant impact on overall macroeconomic results.

1. Introduction

IPCC scenarios that aim to hold the global temperature to acceptable values rely on the large-scale implementation and success of a range of techniques and practices. One area is land-based climate mitigation techniques and practices (LMTs), which is a main focus for carbon sequestration (IPCC, 2022). To understand the realistic potential of LMTs, we first need to assess the risks related to implementation barriers as well as the potential impacts of LMTs.

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In this report, we analyse adoption of LMT portfolios at the national scale in five case study countries: Switzerland, Sweden, the Netherlands, Canada, and Germany. In cooperation with case study leads who collaborate closely with stakeholders, we developed quantified assumptions scenarios regarding the uptake of each LMT within a national portfolio. These quantified assumptions were then entered as inputs into an E3ME modelling scenario, and the results from these scenario model runs were analysed to help draw policy conclusions from the macroeconomic perspective.

The report is organised into two main sections: the first outlining the general methodological approach to the E3ME case study modelling in more detail; and the second presenting the methodology and results for each national case study in turn. Further information on the E3ME model, and on the development of quantitative assumptions, is provided in Annexes.

2. Modelling methodology

2.1 The E3ME model

The macroeconomic impacts of the LMT case studies mentioned in this report are assessed using the E3ME model.

E3ME is a computer-based model of the world's economic and energy systems and the environment. It was originally developed through the European Commission's research framework programmes and is now widely used in Europe and beyond for policy assessment, for forecasting and for research purposes.

E3ME is often used to assess the impacts of environmental and climate mitigation policy on the economy and the labour market. The basic model structure links the economy to the energy system to ensure consistency across each area.

The main dimensions of E3ME are:

- 71 countries – all major world economies, the EU28 and candidate countries plus other countries' economies grouped;
- 44 (or 70 in Europe) industry sectors, based on standard international classifications;
- 28 (or 43 in Europe) categories of household expenditure;
- 25 different users of 12 different fuel types; and
- 14 types of air-borne emission (where data are available) including the 6 GHG's monitored under the Kyoto Protocol.

More information on the E3ME model is provided in Annex 1. A technical model manual of E3ME is available online (Cambridge Econometrics, 2022).

2.2 Scenario modelling

E3ME modelling studies are typically constructed as a comparison between a given scenario (or scenarios) – in which the object of the analysis (in this case, the implementation of an LMT on a national scale) is assumed – and a “business-as-usual” (BAU) baseline in which that policy or activity is absent.

The results from the scenario model runs are then compared to the baseline model results, and the differences between the outcomes are attributed to the impact of the LMT activity alone. The aim of the modelling exercise is not to produce a forecast of the scenario outcome, rather to estimate the impact of the scenario assumptions (e.g. LMT deployment) on the overall outcome. It is therefore typical to present results in terms of the scenario differences from baseline, rather than in absolute values.

2.3 Methodological limitations

In our LMT scenarios, the deployment of LMTs at a national scale is assumed rather than modelled endogenously. That is to say, this study does not assess the impact of *policies* aiming to influence the deployment of these LMTs. We explore in greater depth an assessment of LMT policy mixes in D5.4 “LMT policy portfolios”. Instead, the purpose of this scenario analysis is to assess the consequences of the assumed LMT deployment, in macroeconomic terms, were it to take place: in other words, a “what-if” analysis.

2.4 Stakeholder engagement

For the most part, stakeholder engagement through case study leads was mainly used as a means of developing LMT narratives (part of D2.1 “Case study scaling scenario advanced”) and identifying key LMTs to include in the national LMT portfolio. Stakeholder engagements further helped to refine these narratives, and translate the qualitative narratives of LMT adoption into quantitative assumptions to be used as model inputs. These model inputs were in some cases checked for reasonability with stakeholders, for instance regarding the potential extent of LMT uptake in each national context. In some cases, results from initial model runs were presented as part of a broader set of materials in stakeholder workshops.

2.5 Connections with future work in other work packages

The E3ME modelling scenarios for national LMT portfolios presented in this report build on the development of national case study narratives in D2.1, and the development of case study scaling scenarios in D2.6. They also complement the development of business cases for national LMT case studies in D3.5.

Learning from the development of national-scale E3ME LMT scenarios in this D5.5 report will feed into the development and modelling of a global-scale LMT scenario in D7.4 “Economic and environmental effects of LMT implementation”. The process of developing scenario narratives, developing model scenario designs and quantifying inputs for national-level LMT case studies in T5.5 “E3ME model simulations” is an important building block in understanding of applicability of different LMTs in different national/regional contexts, developing cost assumptions, and so on.

3. Case studies

3.1 Switzerland case study

3.1.1 *Narrative*

Soils are the largest terrestrial carbon pool in active exchange with the atmosphere and store more than double the amount of carbon than the biomass (Lal, 2004). Soil management options that enhance the amount of carbon in soils are thus effective LMTs from a carbon emissions perspective. Soil carbon is in constant turnover, new carbon formation and turnover of present carbon happen simultaneously, and thus enhancing soil carbon stocks in contrast to other NETs has an element of impermanence.

The two ways to alter soil carbon stocks are either slowing down the decomposition of soil carbon or increasing the input of new carbon into the soil. Reduced tillage addresses the first way, as tillage breaks up soil aggregates thereby effectively increasing the speed of carbon cycling in the soil (Six et al., 1999). Organic agriculture, meanwhile, can increase the amount of carbon input into the soil, leading to soil carbon sequestration (Smith, et al., 2019). However, we still need to verify this in our LMT case studies via in-situ monitoring (see D3.4 Calibration and validation Report).

Reduced tillage and organic agriculture practices are associated with further environmental co-benefits and trade-offs. The increase of soil carbon stocks has also several co-benefits, as it improves water holding- and nutrient storage capacities, soil structure and soil aeration. For reduced tillage practices, there exists the risk of an increased pest pressure from either higher pressure from weeds in the field, or from higher fungal growth on crop residues remaining on the soil surface. This could thus lead to an increased need to apply pesticides, which could both negatively affect biodiversity and water quality. In contrast, organic farming can improve biodiversity due to more diverse crop rotations (Smith, et al., 2019) Also, a lower load of nutrients, as no synthetic fertilizers are used and livestock units are coupled to cultivated land area in organic agriculture, could lead to reduced N₂O emissions and reduced nitrate leaching, also improving the water quality (Scialabba & Müller-Lindenlauf, 2010).

Swiss agricultural policy has implemented several regulations addressing these LMTs. This includes subsidies for measures that are stated to increase resource use efficiency, which includes no-till and reduced tillage practices, and further subsidies available for practitioners of organic agriculture.

Of the different LMTs discussed, organic farming is the most widely applied. Currently, 16% of Swiss farmers are already practicing organic farming (Federal Statistical office of Switzerland, 2021) and the number has been constantly growing in the last years. Additionally, according to official statistics, reduced tillage subsidies have been paid for about 82,000 ha in 2019, which is about 7.5 % of agricultural area in Switzerland (Federal Office for Agriculture of Switzerland, 2020).

Another critical point when it comes to organic agriculture is the reduced yields per area, compared to conventional agriculture. For example, compared to conventional agriculture, organic farming

requires between 20 (cereals, pulses) and 80% (vegetables, animal products) more land on a per calories basis (Clark, 2017).

3.1.2 Stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement from the scoping and narrative development phase directly influenced the first scenarios that were modelled in E3ME (e.g., short-listing of LMTs, ambition, extent of LMT application). Six interviews were conducted in the scoping phase (March to May, 2021) helping with the short-listing and defining the LMTs to be considered with E3ME and other models, another ten interviews were conducted to find out the key risks and general perspective of different LMTs (May to July, 2022). The learnings of the latter informed the narratives which were used to develop the earliest version of the storylines. We define storylines as the scenarios that can be modelled based on narratives co-developed with stakeholders and case study leads.

As of now, E3ME was used to simulate the earliest version of the storylines. The initial E3ME model results were raised in the first online stakeholder workshop in February 2023 with ten participants (more food imports needed with more LMTs, overall economic effect small) but not discussed in a lot of detail because the main goal of the workshop was to derive missing input for the other models. More detailed storylines were developed in the second in-person workshop (August 2023, nine participants). The current E3ME results are based on the initial narrative and roughly correspond to the medium ambition scenario of these updated scenarios. It is envisioned to update the E3ME results in the coming months to be in alignment with scenarios from other models.

3.1.3 Scenario design

For the Switzerland case study, three scenarios were developed, based on two key LMTs identified for Switzerland:

- A **“No tillage”** scenario, assuming uptake of the “No tillage” LMT
- An **“Organic farming”** scenario, assuming uptake of the “Organic farming” LMT
- A **“Combined”** scenario, assuming uptake of both the “No tillage” and “Organic farming” LMTs.

LMT deployment

The “No tillage” and “Organic farming” LMTs represent alternative crop management systems. In each LMT scenario, the LMT is assumed to be implemented on a certain share of agricultural land used for each crop nationally by 2050, with different LMT adoption assumptions for different crop types. The LMT adoption assumptions are defined in terms of additional land shares for no tillage and organic farming LMTs relative to baseline land shares. The extent of the land shares in which each LMT is assumed to be adopted for each crop was agreed in consultation with the Swiss case study lead.

The implementation of LMTs is assumed to follow an “S-curve” shaped diffusion profile, with increasing rates of adoption as the LMT is scaled up in more and more areas. This adoption rate is assumed to be strongest in the period of the late 2030s and early 2040s, as the technology matures in the national scale.

The “Combined” scenario assumes both LMTs are adopted in these national shares of agricultural production. However, reduced tillage systems are effectively incompatible with organic agricultural methods. This is because in reduced tillage systems, herbicides such as glyphosate are often applied to reduce the competition for the crop by killing of the established weed cover prior seeding. On the other hand, synthetic herbicides are excluded in organic agriculture and to manage weed pressure, ploughing is usually the best option. Therefore, the “Combined” scenario assumes both LMTs are adopted nationally, but on separate plots rather than overlapping on the same plot.

Table 1: Assumed additional share of Switzerland agricultural land area under LMT management by 2050, by scenario

Agricultural produce	No tillage land share additions	Organic farming land share additions	Combined land share additions
1 Cereals	20%	20%	40%
2 Rice	0%	10%	10%
3 Potatoes	25%	25%	50%
4 Other roots	15%	10%	25%
5 Maize	15%	10%	25%
6 Soy	15%	10%	25%
7 Sunflower	10%	10%	20%
8 Rapeseed	10%	10%	20%
9 Other oil crops	10%	10%	20%
10 Sugar crops	0%	10%	10%
11 Poultry	0%	10%	10%
12 Pork	0%	25%	25%
13 Beef	0%	20%	20%
14 Other meat & animal products	0%	0%	0%
15 Fish	0%	0%	0%
16 Dairy	0%	20%	20%
17 Fruit	0%	25%	25%
18 Vegetables	0%	30%	30%
19 Other	0%	0%	0%

Adopting reduced tillage and organic agriculture LMTs would drive up the cost of agricultural production (or equivalently reduce yields for the same cost of inputs). We developed further assumptions regarding these cost impacts of LMTs on domestic agricultural production, for each category of produce. These production cost assumptions, together with the land use share assumptions, were used to calculate a weighted impact on the prices of overall domestic production of the crop (accounting for the fact that LMTs only affect part of the crop production). The price impacts per crop were then combined into a weighted average price impact on output of the

agricultural sector as a whole (shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**). These domestic agricultural price impacts were then entered into the model as a scenario input.

More details on the reasoning behind the numerical assumptions in **Error! Reference source not found.** can be found in Annex 2.2.

Figure 1: Assumed LMT price impact on domestic agricultural output by scenario, 2020-2050, % difference from baseline

Methodological limitations

We do not provide an assessment of the GHG impacts of the LMT scenarios in this case study. This is principally due to the fact that estimates of potential carbon removals and storage, as well as their permanence, are still relatively uncertain, and highly dependent on a number of factors which vary by location. While assessment of GHG impacts of these LMTs is excluded from the analysis of the Switzerland case study in this D5.5 report, this assessment is included in other work packages within the LANDMARC consortium (e.g. see D3.4 Calibration and validation Report).

3.1.4 Modelling results

Economic impacts

The upward price shock on domestic agricultural output produces negative macroeconomic outcomes for the Swiss economy. These negative impacts are, however, relatively small in the context of the overall Swiss economy, with a GDP impact of -0.14% (€1.2bn) relative to the baseline by 2050 in the Combined scenario, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Most of the negative impact in the Combined scenario is driven by the adoption of organic agriculture rather than no tillage methods. This is partly because our assumptions implied that organic agriculture has a larger negative impact on yields of various crops, but also because we have

assumed that organic agricultural practices are applied to a wider range of agricultural products, including meat and dairy production.

Figure 2: GDP and components by scenario, 2020-2050, differences from baseline, 2020 € billion and %

The breakdown of outcomes by GDP component shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** also demonstrate that much of the negative impact to the Swiss economy is reflected in a reduction in net exports (i.e., an increase in imports), rather than domestic consumption or investment. This reflects the fact that as prices of domestic agricultural output increase, domestic consumers would tend to substitute to imported agricultural produce, rather than bear the cost of higher food prices. This would then lead to a rise in imports compensating for a fall in domestic production, which has a negative impact on GDP.

This negative impact on domestic agricultural production would create multiplier effects that affect the rest of the Swiss economy. In particular, the reduction in demand for domestic agricultural produce would result in the loss of around 8,000 jobs in the agricultural sector in the Combined scenario (as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**). Lower employment at the aggregate level reduces household incomes, which in turn leads to a reduction in consumer expenditure, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. Since consumer expenditure is relatively more stable than incomes, the fall in consumer expenditure lags the fall in household incomes, and so there are expected to be further reductions in consumer expenditure beyond the end of the analysed scenario period in 2050.

Figure 3: Employment, Combined scenario, 2020-2050, absolute differences from baseline, '000s jobs

3.1.5 Conclusions

The negative macroeconomic impacts produced in our Switzerland LMT scenarios show the economic risks of adopting lower-yield crop and livestock management techniques, due to their impact on higher agricultural prices. The Swiss agricultural sector bears the brunt of much of these negative impacts, as Swiss consumers are relatively insulated from higher costs of domestic production by switching to imported agricultural goods. However, the GDP impacts are non-negligible, with our results suggesting that implementing this LMT portfolio would lead to losses in GDP terms on the order of 0.3% relative to the baseline, leading to the loss of around 20,000 agricultural jobs. This raises the risk that imposition of regulatory requirements to implement these LMTs in the Swiss agricultural sector may meet with considerable social and political opposition from affected stakeholders.

This highlights the importance of providing models of LMT policy which address these potentially economic negative impacts for key stakeholders (e.g., farmers) even through there could be longer term climate mitigation benefits for general society. One such model could involve offering carbon credits to farmers which implement these LMTs and store additional carbon in their soil. However, since reliable estimates of this soil carbon sequestration are currently not yet provided for a larger scale, we have not assessed the emissions impacts of this LMT portfolio, and hence have not considered carbon credits as part of our E3ME modelling scenarios. For the Swiss case study, other models including the DayCent model (D5.3 Modelling simulations for LMT scaling at the national level) and in-situ soil sampling techniques work carried out in WP3 first estimates of carbon mitigation potential (See D3.3. In Situ Measurements Data Collection Report; D3.5 Best management practices guide”; and D3.6 “LMTs monitoring effectiveness on assessing potential carbon mitigation efforts can provide first insights to the impact of organic farming. Results from D5.3, D3.3, D3.5 and

D3.6 can then be translated to provide a new business case for the potential CO₂ revenue streams resulting from LMT farming practices. We intend to publish these results in subsequent papers.

3.2 Sweden case study

3.2.1 *Narrative*

The Swedish case study focuses on the potential for two alternative biofuel-based land-management techniques (LMTs) to generate carbon removals in Sweden: bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and biochar.

These two carbon removal technologies are particularly suited to the Swedish context for different reasons. Bioenergy is already a widespread and mature technology in the Swedish energy system, and therefore there is a relatively strong potential for this to be converted to a negative emissions technology by simply adding CCS infrastructure.

The large potential of BECCS to help to achieve Sweden's climate targets was affirmed by a commission appointed by the Swedish Government in 2018 to investigate how a "climate positive" future can be achieved for the country. The main task of the commission was to investigate three types of measures for negative emissions: (i) land-use, land-use change and forestry sector activities (LULUCF); (ii) BECCS; and (iii) verified emission reductions (VER) in other countries (Ministry of the environment & Government offices of Sweden, 2020).

Meanwhile, biochar is a more nascent technology in Sweden, which already has a developed bioeconomy (Fischer, Stenius, & Holmgren, 2019), but also has potential for scaling and replication in different locations depending on different country contexts (Azzi, Karlton, & Sundberg, 2021). Biochar can have many applications, from soil improvement leading to higher crop yields (improves water retention, good soil bacteria and reduces the need for chemical fertilisers), to acting as an animal feed supplement or water filtration (Onnu, 2023). This explains why biochar has been pursued as an LMT in Sweden, despite its somewhat limited national applicability as well as the lower potential associated with the northern European climate. The wide applicability of biochar, especially in agriculture in lower income countries (Karan, Woolf, Azzi, Sundberg, & Wood, 2023), is of strategic interest for Sweden because of its international cooperation efforts and its commitment to investments in measures outside of Sweden to as to support pathways to negative emissions internationally as well as domestically (Sundberg & Azzi, 2023).

BECCS is a key LMT in the Swedish context in reaching zero and negative emission targets, but the land use side is less relevant because so much land in Sweden is already managed and optimised for biomass supply and bioenergy (Kumar, Adamopoulos, & Jones, 2021). Consequently, the main issues of concern are related to biomass supply from existing production areas and the (non-land) issues associated with carbon dioxide transport and storage. Since CO₂ storage is expected to occur outside of Sweden (e.g., Norway) there are also some implementation issues that remain unresolved (Fuss & Johnsson, 2021), in addition to other uncertainties associated with a new technology.

3.2.2 *Stakeholder engagement*

Previous stakeholder engagement in relation to the Sweden E3ME case study modelling includes a series of interviews conducted in 2022, framed under a Master thesis project at KTH. The interviews

served as a two-step platform to gather inputs for the E3ME model. Qualitative and quantitative information collected in the interviews was first processed by the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI), a partner in the LANDMARC project, to obtain economic and technology range parameters for biochar and BECCS in Sweden. Specific publications (e.g. on BECCS costs) that were recommended by stakeholders helped quantify the model input parameters. Then, this data was provided to E3ME and applied in the model.

The interviews, 9 in total, were conducted online from March to April of 2022. Stakeholders from business, academia, research, consultancy, and civil society participated. The variety of backgrounds was a positive driver for the collection of technical and economic trends for the development of biochar and bioenergy carbon capture and storage (BECCS) in the Swedish context. BECCS in particular is a rather new technology, and Sweden is among the frontrunners with implementation, so these data helped improve E3ME input data. The stakeholder insights helped us develop the contextual narratives that gave base to the modelling exercise. A particularly useful input from stakeholder was regarding type of applications and sectors where biochar and BECCS can be applied.

E3ME model results have not been employed in stakeholder engagement. SEI is additionally planning for regional stakeholder engagements in the last quarter of 2023, which are not specifically planned for obtaining further inputs for the E3ME modelling, but they can offer important policy insights that can be later tested in E3ME. E3ME model results will be mentioned as necessary, but to a limited extent since the modelling is for Sweden, not the EU.

We plan for a separate policy brief summarising the Swedish E3ME case study results to be published under the umbrella of SEI peer-reviewed publication. Then in collaboration with our colleagues working with communication we will disseminate the results to relevant stakeholders.

3.2.3 Scenario design

A BECCS and biochar uptake scenario (LMT scenario) is constructed in E3ME with a set of modelling inputs, summarised in **Error! Reference source not found.** below. The results from this E3ME scenario run are compared against results from a model run that represents the business as usual case (baseline).¹

The LMT scenario runs from 2026-2045. BECCS and biochar technologies are assumed to be ready for deployment by 2025 at the earliest (Stockholm Exergi, 2023). Assumptions for CO₂ removals are set according to targets specified for 2045, the year when Sweden aims to achieve net zero greenhouse gas emissions (Sweden Ministry of the Environment, 2020).

¹ The BAU projection for energy demand in E3ME is constructed based on the PRIMES 2016 reference case (European Commission, 2016), while BAU projections of macroeconomic variables are based on the IIASA SSP2 “Middle of the Road” Baseline pathway modelled with MESSAGE-GLOBIOM (IIASA, 2018).

It should be noted that these deployment outcomes are estimated based on stakeholder knowledge rather than modelled. This study does not assess the impact of *policies* aiming to influence the deployment of these technologies. Instead, the purpose of this scenario analysis is to assess the consequences of this deployment, in macroeconomic terms, if this deployment were to take place.

More details on the reasoning behind the numerical assumptions in **Error! Reference source not found.** can be found in Annex 2.2.

Table 2: Summary of model inputs for BECCS & biochar scenario

Variable	BECCS	Biochar
Annual CO ₂ removal	10.7 MtCO ₂ by 2045	1.8 MtCO ₂ by 2045
Energy demand	See Annex 2	
CAPEX	€56/tCO ₂	€90/tCO ₂
OPEX	€53/tCO ₂	€9/tCO ₂
Carbon credits	2025: €24/tCO ₂ 2045: €42/tCO ₂	2025: €48/tCO ₂ 2045: €84/tCO ₂

Note: All financial values in this table are assumed to be in constant 2022 prices.

LMT deployment

Deployment of BECCS and biochar technologies is assumed, rather than modelled exogenously as a result of targeted policy measures. A quantity of CO₂ removals for each technology is assumed for the modelling by 2045. The assumptions are in line with the authorities' analysis for CO₂ removals per technology proposed to achieve the national net zero GHG emissions target.

These deployment levels are associated with changes in energy demand (namely for biofuels), as well as changes in expenditure flows tied to techno-economic cost assumptions for the respective LMTs.

Carbon credits

The carbon prices assumed in this scenario represent a hypothetical government program of carbon credits, paid to firms that generate carbon removals through BECCS and biochar LMTs. The assumptions are made by the modelling team in dialogue with the Swedish case study team.

On the seller's side, we model these carbon credits as net reductions in firms' operational expenditure (OPEX) costs. On the purchaser's side, the credits represent additional government spending in our model.

We assume neutral fiscal impact, so government must raise other taxes (income tax, VAT) to balance budget.

Separate carbon prices are assumed for BECCS and biochar, due to the relative advantages of biochar in terms of the permanence of carbon removals (Honegger, Poralla, Michaelowa, & Ahonen, 2021). The market price for biochar is modelled as double that of BECCS, per the CORC Carbon Removal Price Index Carbon price. CO₂ prices are assumed to follow PRIMES projections of the EU ETS price.

Revenue recycling

The concept of “revenue recycling” refers to the idea that additional government revenues from carbon taxes are recycled into the economy, through either spending increases or reductions in other tax rates. Without these counterbalancing measures, the net effect of a higher carbon tax would be a fiscal contraction.

Our scenarios explore net removals of CO₂ through BECCS and biochar. The modelling team assumed that the carbon pricing scheme explored in these scenarios also applies as a government subsidy for these negative emissions. Since the government spends additional budget on this policy, in this case revenue recycling implies that other tax rates must be *raised* to maintain a balanced budget.

In the “With revenue recycling” scenario, we implement the revenue recycling through increases in income tax, VAT, and employers’ social security rates. In the “No revenue recycling” scenario, the government does not raise these taxes, and so is effectively pursuing an expansionary fiscal policy, i.e., an unfunded subsidy to industry.

Methodological limitations

E3ME does not include feedbacks from biofuel demand to biofuel supply from the agriculture and forestry sectors. Therefore this study excludes an assessment of the impact of BECCS and biochar deployment in Sweden on primary supply of biofuels and associated land use. That said, the impacts from BECCS and biochar deployment on the quantity of biofuel supply would most likely be expected to be minor, as the majority of the biofuel demand used in BECCS and biochar deployment in our scenario represents alternative uses of biofuel demand that is already considered in the baseline (see Annex 2).

3.2.4 Modelling results

a. Environmental impacts

The emissions impacts are dominated by the assumed 12.5 MtCO₂ of removals from the rollout of BECCS infrastructure in the combined heat and power (CHP) and paper and pulp sectors, as well as biochar application.² This represents around 25% of total greenhouse gas emissions in Sweden in 2019 (in CO₂-equivalent terms, excluding LULUCF).³

The small economic impacts (see next section) mean that there are negligible second-order impacts on CO₂ emissions, as shown by the almost invisible “Other” category in Figure 4. This suggests that

² BECCS technology was assumed to be applied in the CHP and paper and pulp sectors, as these are currently the largest consumers of solid biofuels in Sweden. The assumption was based on historical data as well as interviews with stakeholders.

³ According to Sweden’s 2021 UNFCCC National Inventory Report (p23) submitted to the UNFCCC (Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2021), Sweden emitted 50.9 MtCO₂e of GHG emissions in 2019.

there would likely be no rebound effects from the assumed CO₂ removals, nor would there be any synergies in terms of further reductions in emissions from other sectors.

Figure 4: CO₂ emissions, LMT scenario, absolute differences from baseline, MtCO₂

b. Economic impacts

The macroeconomic impact of these LMTs would be small in the context of Swedish economy, with an absolute GDP impact smaller than 0.05% relative to the baseline, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

This suggests that the substantial environmental benefits from increased BECCS and biochar removals would come at a relatively small cost to the Swedish economy (at worst) and could even bring a small economic benefit under certain assumptions (explained in the remainder of this section).

The macroeconomic impact would be positive in the short run, and negative in long run – assuming that tax credits are provided for carbon removals, and governments adjust other taxes to maintain fiscal neutrality (“With revenue recycling” scenario). If this assumption is removed (“No revenue recycling” scenario), then there would be a small positive GDP impact throughout the scenario period.

Figure 5: GDP and components, LMT scenario, differences from baseline, 2020 €m and %

In both scenarios, the initial positive GDP impact is driven by investment in CCS and biochar capacity. This investment boost persists throughout the scenario period due to the linear rollout of capacity.

However, in the “With revenue recycling” scenario the investment impact is soon (in the early 2030s) outweighed by the negative impact on consumer expenditure in the long run. This drop in spending is driven by falling disposable incomes, which are attributable to increasing income tax rates, as the government attempts to replace lost carbon tax revenues with increased revenues elsewhere.

At the same time, in both scenarios, carbon credits push down industry costs and thus industrial prices, and therefore tend to increase the real value of consumers’ disposable income.

However, in the “With revenue recycling” scenario this is outweighed in the long run by rising VAT and social security rates, which is driven by the same dynamics as the raise in income tax rates mentioned above. The net effect is an increase in consumer prices, which reduce the real value of disposable incomes even further.

On the whole, in the “With revenue recycling” scenario lower disposable incomes and higher consumer prices drive a relatively strong reduction in consumer spending. This impact becomes stronger throughout the scenario period, as carbon prices rise and CO₂ removals increase in quantity.

If we remove the assumption of fiscal neutrality (and therefore the increase in income, VAT and social security rates), as in the “No revenue recycling” scenario, then falling industrial prices (from carbon credits) increase the real value of consumer income in both the short and the longer run.⁴

⁴ As prices increase (i.e., with higher inflation), the “real” value (i.e., purchasing power) of consumer incomes is correspondingly diminished, even if the “nominal” value remains unchanged. By the same token, falling prices tend to increase the real value of income.

Consumer spending would see a small corresponding boost, and the overall macroeconomic impact would be marginally positive.

The trend in other GDP components mostly represents the import share of consumption. Higher consumer demand is met in part by imports, and these purchases are subtracted from GDP (as they represent domestic demand rather than domestic product). Hence the results broadly show that “other GDP components” fall as consumption rises, and vice versa.

3.2.5 *Conclusions*

The comparison of results from the two modelled scenarios – BECCS and biochar deployment in Sweden, with and without revenue recycling – shows the critical impact of assumptions around how a public carbon credit system would be funded on overall macroeconomic outcomes. Our modelling suggests that a carbon credit system funded through taxpayer contributions would have a net negative impact on overall macroeconomic outcomes, while a system funded through additional borrowing could have positive impacts, as a result of fiscal stimulus effects.

At the same time, our analysis also suggests that the overall impact of the implementation of this BECCS and biochar LMT portfolio on the macroeconomy is small, whether this carbon credit system is funded through taxpayer contributions or otherwise. A more accurate portrayal of our modelling results is not that the macroeconomic impacts are positive or negative, rather that they are small in the context of the wider Swedish economy. Given the large potential environmental benefits of this LMT portfolio in terms of net emissions reductions, any potential negative macroeconomic impacts from such a taxpayer-funded system may be considered as a relatively small price to pay by policy makers. However, impacts on household expenditures and consumers’ purchasing power should not be neglected, since they might lead to push-backs that can delay successful deployment and risk achievement of the country’s net-zero targets.

3.3 Netherlands case study

3.3.1 *Narrative*

Looking at the Netherlands' greenhouse gas emissions, agricultural and land-use sectors contributed around 13% of total GHG emission in 2020 (National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, RIVM, 2022). Given the current EU and national emission reduction targets, increased efforts would be expected from the agricultural and land-use sectors in order to achieve these ambitions. With this in mind, the Netherlands LMT portfolio focuses on four separate LMTs with potential to store carbon and reduce GHG emissions: peatlands (or paludiculture); forests; agroforestry; and carbon capture, storage or utilisation applied to anaerobic digestion of manure.

The continued draining of peatlands to enable agricultural and other activities (e.g., urban development) leads to an oxidation process which further results into soil subsidence. The oxidation process itself leads to increased CO₂-emissions, while the subsidence process leads to increased damages to infrastructure and buildings.

Of the about 436.000 ha of organic soils, 274.000 ha are so-called peat(y) soils. Most of this land (207.000 ha) is used for agriculture. The other 162.000 ha (of which 130.000 ha is used in agriculture) generally have thinner peat layers (5-40 cm of peat in the top 80cm of soil). The areas where rewetting will likely be conducted, are those areas where soil subsidence is most significant. Soil subsidence due to decades of peat soil drainage is a major driver for current and future damages to houses and infrastructure for the coming decades.

Forests in the Netherlands cover about 340,000 ha, which is just over 8% of the total area. About 55% of the forest (larger than 5 hectares) is owned by public organizations; the remaining is private forest property.

The National Forest Strategy (LNV, 2020) builds upon the agreements made in the National Climate Agreement (Government D. , 2019). It also aims to implement biodiversity policy in the scope of the EU Habitat and Birds Directives. the National Forest Strategy focusses on 1) increasing the national forest area by 10% from 370,000 ha in 2020 to 407,000 ha in 2030 (of which 18.000 ha in existing nature areas, and 19.000 outside nature areas), 2) the revitalization of forests, and 3) increase the number of trees outside forests (TOF). Especially, the expansion of the forest area and TOF outside of the already existing nature areas (i.e., agroforestry – see below) will most likely come at the expense of the land used for agricultural purposes.

Agroforestry in the Netherlands, using land for agroforestry aligns with objectives of multiple policies, such as the National Forest Strategy (Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2020) and the transition to a more circular and nature-inclusive agriculture (Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2018). As outlined in the Dutch Forest Strategy, the total climate impact of agroforestry is quantified as part of the sector goal “trees, forest and nature” with 0.4 Mton CO₂ and 0.8 Mton CO₂ (‘ambitious goal’) in 2030. However, it is not clear yet how much of the aimed GHG emissions are assigned to non-agroforestry in this sector such

as landscape elements. According to (Lesschen et al., 2021), agroforestry could contribute to 0.1 Mton CO₂; however, assuming a more ambitious target of 25,000 ha in 2030 compared to 7,000 ha mentioned in the Dutch Forest Strategy.

Carbon capture and storage or utilisation (CCS/U) applied to anaerobic digestion (AD) based on animal manure is another LMT of the portfolio for the Netherlands. A green gas blending obligation for energy suppliers to the residential sector will be implemented in The Netherlands in 2025. This obligation aims to scale up the production of green gases (biogas, hydrogen) up to at least 1,6 bln. m³ (current production around 220 mln. m³) by 2030 (EZK, 2022). This in turn is expected to result in a 2,9 Mton CO₂ emission reduction (1,8 – 4,9 Mton CO₂/y range estimate) by 2030. These estimated CO₂ savings exclude any potential emission reductions or carbon removal associated with the production and utilization of organic fertilizers (derived from AD digestate), as well as any CO₂ capture and reuse/storage at the biogas plants. As such the net CO₂-savings from AD of animal manure, combined with CCS/U and production of organic fertilizers could be significantly higher. The AD sector is already actively exploring and developing systems that can enable the production of organic fertilizers (to replace mineral fertilizers) and to capture biogenic CO₂ (to replace fossil CO₂ or to store it).

In a report (CE-Delft, 2022) commissioned by the Ministry of Economic Affairs exploring the impact of a blending obligation green gas, assumes a high reliance on AD of animal manure for meeting the set target. It is estimated that around 57% of the biogas will have to originate from animal manure (with 43% originating from other feedstocks). The report also assumes that the green gas production target (for animal manure derived biogas) can be achieved, assuming an assumed 20% (min.) or 30% (max.) reduction in the livestock population. This target will not likely be achieved by reducing the livestock population >30%. The discussion about the size of the Dutch livestock sector is very relevant, since within the current public/political debate regarding NO_x and NH₃ emissions there are several political parties advocating reducing the livestock sector by about 50%.

3.3.2 Stakeholder engagement

Firstly, a literature review was conducted complemented with some targeted stakeholder interviews to elicit a long-list of potentially interesting and viable LMTs.

Secondly, a short-list of LMTs was defined based on the most realistic and feasible LMTs, and for which specific relevant policy targets have been set (see above), i.e., the Dutch LMT portfolio. For all LMTs in the portfolio, the storylines in D2.6 were created, describing key aspects of these LMTs including key challenges and uncertainties related to implementation and upscaling of these practices.

This step was done via literature review and complementary stakeholder engagement work. Seven in-depth stakeholder interviews with agroforestry (3x), peatland (3x) and anaerobic digestion (1x) experts were conducted to assess any potential trade-offs/barriers and co-benefits/opportunities of scaling up the different options in the short-listed LMT portfolio, and three online stakeholder sessions were organised.

On 30 June 2021 an online expert session was organised.⁵ This session focussed on challenges related to GHG monitoring of various LMTs via earth observation techniques.

The first online policy session with 20 participants was organised on 17 December 2021⁶ and focussed on the valorisation of carbon removal in soils, trees, and bio-based products outside the European Emissions Trading Scheme. A smaller follow-up policy session was organised on 7 February 2022 where insights and ideas on policy barriers were exchanged with five bio-economy policy experts.⁷ In addition to that, LANDMARC (represented by JIN) also was invited to discuss policy and valorisation aspects of carbon farming activities in two online events on 8 June 2022⁸ (27 participants), and 14 November 2022 (17 participants) organised by Wageningen University Research as part of an initiative on nutrient recycling ('Leerreis nutriëntenkringloop').

The questions and feedback received from the stakeholders during and after those online sessions provided more detailed insights in the various risks, challenges and barriers (e.g., technical barriers, policy barriers, economic barriers) for scaling up various LMTs as well as opportunities and co-benefits. This supported the scenario development and simulation modelling.

Thirdly, these storylines were translated into model inputs. With support from CE, we have extracted relevant data-points/inputs for modelling and discussed some dynamics. The main aim was to explore all 4 LMTs in the portfolio at once (parallel implementation), since that most adequately reflects the current market/system dynamics within the AFOLU sectors in the country.

Further stakeholder engagement is foreseen in future stakeholder workshops where (preliminary or advanced) simulation modelling results will be shared.

3.3.3 Scenario design

For the Netherlands case study, we developed a single scenario combining a number of LMTs:

- Paludiculture (i.e. peatland rewetting)
- Afforestation
- Agroforestry
- Anaerobic digestion of manure

Model input assumptions were developed for each LMT regarding the adoption of the LMT in terms of land area, associated emissions, impacts on energy demand, and economic costs. These input assumptions are summarised in the following sections. More details on the development of these assumptions are provided in Annex 2.

⁵ <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/news/landmarc-leads-a-dutch-carbon-mapping-collaboration>

⁶ <https://www.mestverwaarding.nl/kenniscentrum/2463/de-valorisatie-van-koolstofvastlegging-in-bodems-bossen-en-bio-based-producten-buiten-het-europese-emissiehandels-systeem>

⁷ <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/news/landmarc-opens-policy-dialogue-on-carbon-farming-and-carbon-removal-valorization-with-the-dutch-bio-economy-federation>

⁸ <https://edepot.wur.nl/587011>

a. LMT deployment

Based on the combination of the results of the literature review and various stakeholder engagement actions (interviews and online sessions) specific assumptions were developed by the researchers for the extent of adoption of each LMT by 2050, shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. Further refinements to these assumptions were developed for the trajectory of this LMT adoption over time, and the time series of the land use shares were then applied to historical land-use data from FAOSTAT, to calculate a projection of land-use in thousands of km², shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**.

Table 3: Scenario LMT land share assumptions, %

LMT	Land type converted	Share of land type area converted
Paludiculture	Peatland	40%
Afforestation	Agricultural land	10%
	Pastureland	10%
Agroforestry	Agricultural land	25%
Anaerobic digestion of manure	Pastureland	25% ⁹

Figure 6: Scenario land-use assumptions, thousands km²

b. Economic impacts

These land use changes are also associated with a number of economic impacts assumed in the model. Firstly, the land-use change is directly associated with an increase in investment expenditure, for instance in the purchase of land, saplings, and costs of planting trees for the afforestation LMT.

⁹ In the case of anaerobic digestion of manure, the "land share" effectively refers to the proportion of manure which is assumed to be treated in this manner.

Secondly, these changes in investment (as well as operating) expenditures are assumed to increase unit costs for the agricultural sector, which increases prices of agricultural outputs for domestic and foreign consumers. Finally, the changes in land use effectively reduce the available land for full agricultural exploitation, and hence we have assumed a reduction in agricultural output, implemented through a reduction in agricultural exports, in proportion to the land area lost.

Further economic input assumptions are associated with the damages from soil subsidence as a result of continued draining of peatland. These costs include damage to buildings and infrastructure, which require investment from consumers and firms to repair, as well as increased costs of water management. These costs are assumed to be incurred in the baseline but avoided in the LMT scenario due to efforts to rewet peatlands and prevent subsidence.

3.3.4 Modelling results

a. Environmental impacts

As shown in Figure 7, our modelling suggests that the LMTs included in the scenario would collectively contribute to around a 4 MtCO_{2e} reduction in net annual GHG emissions by 2050, either through carbon removals or avoided emissions, equivalent to around 2% of the Netherlands' current emissions. These emissions impacts were calculated off-model: details on this calculation are provided in Annex 2.3.¹⁰

In our scenario there would be a relatively even contribution of these net emissions reductions across the LMTs analysed, with afforestation, peatland rewetting, and manure management each contributing 0.4-1.3 MtCO_{2e} annual GHG reductions by 2050. A further 1.3 MtCO_{2e} of emissions reductions would be produced in the power generation sector, as we have assumed the biogas produced in the manure anaerobic digestion process would be used in a BECCS negative emissions power plant, displacing electricity generation from fossil fuels.

¹⁰ Emissions impacts are necessarily calculated off-model, as E3ME is an E3 (economy-energy-environment) model which does not currently include a land-use module, and therefore does not track important variables (such as land use) which would be important for this calculation.

Figure 7: Scenario GHG emissions impacts by source, absolute difference from baseline, MtCO₂e

b. Economic impacts

The scenario results indicate that this LMT portfolio would have net negative macroeconomic impacts, with GDP around €8 billion (0.7%) below baseline by 2050.

These negative impacts are largely driven by reductions in agricultural exports. We assumed that agricultural production would be scaled down in line with land use, and that this lower agricultural output would translate into lower exports, thereby directly contributing to GDP.

At the same time, implementation costs of these LMTs for the agricultural sector have contrasting impacts on investment and consumer expenditure. Investment requirements for afforestation, agroforestry and paludiculture measures directly add to the investment expenditure component of GDP, but these and additional operating expenditures drive up units costs for the sector, which is passed on to consumers through higher prices for the sector's output. This inflationary effect reduces households' incomes in real terms, and leads to a corresponding reduction in consumer expenditure, which offsets the positive effects of the investment expenditure on aggregate demand.

Figure 8: GDP and components by scenario, 2020-2060, differences from baseline, 2020 € billion and %

3.3.5 Conclusions

The macroeconomic results from this E3ME case study analysis illustrate the important trade-offs that come with expanding LMTs at a national scale, especially in a country with such contested land area as the Netherlands. The agricultural sector is a major land user and economic sector for the country, and an important driver of exports for the country. In our scenario, we have assumed that the expansion of LMTs in the country would reduce the land available for agricultural production, and therefore lead to a contraction in output for the agricultural sector. Among the many elements considered and inputs included in our scenario, it is this key factor which dominates the overall results, and drives negative macroeconomic outcomes for our scenario, relative to the baseline.

A key consideration for policymakers is therefore what degree of political opposition any regulation to enforce LMT uptake would generate, in what is already a contested political issue in the country. Negative outcomes for key stakeholders, including farmers, may still be considered justified in terms of the wider societal benefits from reduced emissions of greenhouse gases and other pollutants as a result of LMT uptake. However, farmers and other land use owners also need to be compensated for the higher (production) costs they bear that benefits society as a whole in the longer run. Policy will need to be designed carefully in order to balance the needs of these different stakeholders.

3.4 Canada case study

3.4.1 *Narrative*

Canada, being home to 25% of the world's peatlands (Wildlife Conservation Society Canada, 2023), is particularly well suited to peatland restoration. Alongside their environmental benefits as large-scale carbon sinks, peatlands are highly beneficial ecologically as habitats of important local flora and fauna and have high cultural and spiritual significance to Indigenous communities. In 2016, the Pan Canadian Framework (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016) released a plan for how Canada would like to achieve GHG reduction targets, focussing primarily on ecosystem conservation and restoration.

The Canadian federal government has acknowledged the potential negative emissions offered by land-based carbon sequestration approaches (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2020), but movement to incorporate them into national GHG emission reduction strategies has been limited (Riehl and Peters, 2021). Despite this limited uptake on a national scale, there has been some uptake regionally such as in Alberta, where the 'Alberta Wetland Policy' (Government of Alberta, 2013) was put in place to conserve and restore their peatlands. Land under the policy is managed by avoiding and minimizing interference where possible and restoring where it is not. However, a major concern raised by Hyunh (2018) regarding the Alberta Wetland Policy is that it excludes projects approved before July 4th 2016, thereby excluding the majority of the oil sands (also referred to colloquially as tar sands) mining projects in northern Alberta, where the peatlands and oil sands overlap. As such, important peat and wetlands which overlap with oil are left unprotected and degraded.

3.4.2 *Stakeholder engagement*

There has been continuous stakeholder engagement with Elders in the First Nation (Indigenous) community of Fort McKay, Alberta and the community's Sustainability Office since October 2010. The Indigenous community is located within the oil sands region and is the focus of our stakeholder engagement. The community consists of Cree and Dene peoples. These informal meetings with individuals from the community or representing some of the community's interest helped to define their needs relating to land use in the surrounding Boreal forests in the Athabasca region. Wetlands or 'muskeg' -the Cree word for wetlands - are integral to the Boreal forests; thus afforestation and restoration also must consider the protection and restoration of wetlands. Muskeg surrounds the community and has been heavily impacted by activities from the oil and gas sector and other industrial sectors that have created cut lines of over tens of thousands of kilometres in forests. The Muskeg has a vital role in supporting biodiversity and also has high spiritual significance. Thus this has been a driver for focusing on wetland and afforestation in the case study.

Below we include a description of 'Muskeg', written by Cecilia Fitzpatrick, an elder in the Fort McKay First Nation community who comes from a family of Hereditary Chiefs. These words have a significant personal and spiritual meaning and are deeply connected to Cecilia's father's teachings. Her father, Philip McDonald, was Fort McKay First Nation's last hereditary Chief for 27 years and passed away in 1976.

Cecilia Fitzpatrick

My father would tell me that our body is like the Earth that the Muskeg is your heart and that the mountains are your brain, and the creeks and rivers are blood vessels muskeg is very important to rivers and creeks and everything in them - with that comes our spiritual values and how we are connected to and respect the Earth.

When you take from the Earth you always put something back.

- The muskeg is why the Earth breathes.
- We treat the Earth with respect - it's like treating your own body with respect. We take ^{care} of ourselves to live a life of longevity to maintain a life of health and happiness. We need to treat our Earth the same way.

We have carried out further engagement in July 2023 and field work in August 1-4th in the community of Fort McKay. The research team spoke to Elders, youths and key community members to discuss the community's experience and priorities. Some of the more immediate challenges the community faces include affordable and healthy food, clean air and access to healthy land for their traditional practices including picking berries and trapping. Currently we are not modelling the potential for own food generation via greenhouses in E3ME due to scalar issues but would like to capture this in the scenario story lines and possibly in the ALCES models (see D5.3)

The second stakeholder engagement occurred on August 8th, 2023 in Calgary, a city in Alberta that is the economic centre that supports the energy sector. There were 17 stakeholders that represented the conventional energy sector, consulting firms, private innovation companies, not-for-profit organisations, private citizens, academics, university students, community farmers. A key Indigenous Fort McKay community member also participated remotely to emphasise the importance of sustainable food and land use to the workshop participant. The stakeholder workshop revealed that participants saw potential futures in nature based solutions, renewable energy, regenerative farming, wetlands restoration and was cautious about bio-energy capture and storage. Overall stakeholders saw a future beyond the oil and gas sector.

The stakeholder engagement activities conducted in continuous and specifically in 2023, provided information to define credible scenarios for E3ME that are relevant to local stakeholders.

3.4.3 Scenario design

The LMT scenario is constructed in E3ME with a set of modelling inputs, summarised in this section. The results from this E3ME scenario run are compared against results from a baseline model run. The LMT scenario runs from 2022-2050.

The LMT scenario was developed in collaboration with the case study researchers who helped to convey some key stakeholder interests. Note that these scenarios are not intended to represent the stakeholder groups themselves but are researchers' interpretation based on stakeholder consultation and publicly available policy documents.

The scenario assumes that the afforestation and peatland rewetting LMTs are applied on forest and peatland which has been degraded in recent decades through exploitation of bitumen oil deposits in Alberta. Our scenario furthermore assumes that this restoration of forest and peatland areas is accompanied by a drop in oil production, in line with scenarios produced by the Canada Energy Regulator (CER), which makes more degraded land areas available for restoration. The case study research teams assume that the restoration activity – if carried out appropriately and respectfully in consultation with Indigenous communities – can have positive social impact, emission reduction outcomes, and is associated with certain running costs, but also generates revenues through the sale of carbon credits.

The development of scenario assumptions and model inputs is described briefly below; further detail on the assumptions used in the scenario can be found in Annex 2.

a. Oil production

Our LMT scenario assumes a reduced rate of oil extraction relative to the baseline. The trajectories for bitumen production (by extraction technology - "in situ" and "mined" extraction) are taken from scenarios from the CER "Canada's Energy Future 2021", shown in Figure 9: Canada bitumen production by scenario and type, 1970-2050 Figure 9: baseline oil production is assumed to follow the "Current Policies Scenario" (CPS), while oil production in the LMT scenario is assumed to follow the "Evolved Policies Scenario" (EPS).

Figure 9: Canada bitumen production by scenario and type, 1970-2050

b. Land use

Bitumen production is assumed to degrade forestland and peatland where extraction sites are located. Model assumptions are developed regarding the number of hectares affected per unit of oil produced, as well as the lifetime of each extraction site, to develop a profile of the land area “exploited” by oil extraction activities over time in each scenario. The modelling team has also used the same assumptions to estimate the land area over time of “abandoned” sites, where oil reserves have been exhausted, the extraction industry is no longer active, and therefore land is made available for restoration.

In the LMT scenario, we assume that restoration activity is rolled out on these “abandoned” sites (based on stakeholders insights to reclaim degraded land) in a steadily accelerating fashion: each year there is a linear increase in the amount of land restored, and therefore the total area restored increases quadratically. In this LMT scenario, we assume that all “abandoned” sites are restored by 2050. In the baseline, we assume no restoration activity takes place, and “abandoned” sites therefore remain “degraded”. The resulting land use assumptions are illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Land use by scenario, 1970-2050

c. Emissions

The land affected by oil production and restoration activities is, in reality, a complicated mixture of forest and peatland. For simplicity, the modelling team has developed separate assumptions for annual emissions over time from degraded and restored forestland and peatland, and have furthermore assumed that the affected land area consists of 50% forestland and 50% peatland (Elmes, et al., 2021).¹¹

Figure 11 below illustrates the total assumed annual GHG emissions from “exploited”, “degraded” and “restored” plots of land in both the baseline and LMT scenarios.¹² The reduction in emissions between the baseline and scenario degraded plots reflects the reduced rate of oil extraction and we assume that plots of land are fully exhausted before new plots are cleared for new extraction.

¹¹ Details on these assumptions are described in Annex 2.4.

¹² N.B.: The emissions of ‘restored’ plots in the baseline is zero as there are no restored plots in the baseline scenario.

Figure 11: CO2 emissions over the course of the modelled period

d. Restoration costs

The assumed costs of restoration are illustrated in Figure 12 below. They are dominated by the land reclamation cost of 3750 CAD/ha, following the assumptions of Drever et al (2021, Supplementary Info (SI), page 38). Salary costs are highest at the beginning of the project’s lifetime as it becomes established, and monitoring costs rise steadily as the quantity of land being restored increases.

Figure 12: Assumed costs of peatland restoration broken down by component, 2010 €m

e. Restoration revenues (carbon credits)

The restoration LMT is funded through revenues from carbon credits to the value of CAD 300/tCO₂ is introduced gradually from 2020-2025 in order to ease the transition from the existing carbon price in place in Canada. This cost was chosen to reflect the environmental cost of peatland degradation as well as social benefits of the restoration project to local Indigenous communities. Restoration revenues are also a potential new source of revenue generation for local Indigenous communities due to the large area that will need to be reclaimed. This can also create jobs locally in consulting work, tree growing and tree planning to reclaim land that is appropriate for the region, rather than as previously practiced by industry. According to stakeholder engagement insights, previous examples of industry-claimed land involved replanting trees that were not native to the area and did not include proper consultation with local Indigenous communities. Thus, the land is currently seen as not suitable for traditional Indigenous practices.

Table 4: Summary of model inputs for restoration scenario

Variable	Input
CO ₂ removal	613 ktCO ₂ by 2050
Carbon price	CAD 300/tCO ₂ (€342/tCO ₂)
Reclamation costs	3750 CAD/ha
Other sectoral costs	See Annex 2

Note: All financial values in this table are assumed to be in constant 2022 prices.

3.4.4 Modelling results

a. Environmental impacts

The environmental impacts of this scenario are relatively small, accounting for a 4% reduction in overall CO₂ emissions compared to the baseline scenario.

The direct environmental impacts of the scenario are the negative emissions generated by the peatland restoration itself. However, this change in emissions seen in the land use sector is dwarfed when compared to the change in emissions in the oil extraction sector, as shown in Figure 13 below.

Figure 13: Emissions reductions in 'Other energy' and 'Land use' sectors

The oil extraction sector sees a 21 MtCO₂e reduction in GHG emissions by 2050, the largest reduction in any sector. This indicates that the reduced rate of oil extraction modelled in the scenario is the driving force behind the environmental impacts seen in the scenario, rather than the direct negative emissions generated by the peatland restoration itself.

b. Economic impacts

The economic impacts of this scenario are larger overall than the environmental ones, with the scenario showing a 2% reduction in Canada's GDP by 2050 (the end of the modelled period). As shown by Figure 4 below, the main drivers of this impact are consumption, exports, and investment.

Figure 14: Impact of LMT scenario on GDP, broken down by component

Much of this macroeconomic impact is driven by the shrinking of the oil and gas sector in Canada, which is influenced by global and national policies which reduced demand for high-carbon energy. The largest sectoral changes within investment and exports are both seen in the oil and gas sector (18.7% and 15.7% reductions respectively by 2050). The reduction in consumption is driven by the 1.5% reduction in disposable incomes compared to the baseline, which is in turn driven by reduced incomes and employment, both of which are reduced primarily in the oil and gas sector (18.7% reduction in both wages and employment in the oil & gas sector).

3.4.5 Conclusions

The overall shrinking of Canadian GDP in the scenario relative to the baseline indicates that the revenues earned from the peatland restoration project's negative emissions are not offset by the shrinking of the oil & gas sector, even with the high carbon price of 300 CAD/tCO₂ in place.

As with other national case studies analysed in this report, there is a clear trade-off between the environmental and economic benefits brought by the restoration activity, and the decline in the economic activity from the competing land use that is replaced. However, in this case the decline in Canadian oil production is not directly a result of the upscaling of the LMT – rather it is explained by global climate and energy policy trends, and the LMT is implemented only on land which has been vacated by the oil industry. That said, the scenario does indicate that the lost economic output from

a forced shutdown of the oil industry is unlikely to be fully replaced by carbon credits for restoration activities. The scenario also does not assess the added value of eco-systems services including the protective and improvement of Indigenous traditional practices, reduced pollutions and health impacts; thus results are limited in showing societal benefits.

3.5 Germany case study

3.5.1 *Narrative*

With a third of its land area being forested, the carbon sink potential of that land is crucial to Germany's potential for negative emissions. German forests show considerable negative emissions, causing the LULUCF sector to be a net sink for decades (Prognos, Öko-Institut, Wuppertal-Institut, 2020). However, recently the net balance of emissions and removals in the sector switched to a net source (Umweltbundesamt, 2023). The main reason for this change is a decline in the forest sink due to increased disturbances and wood harvest.

The forestry industry in Germany is relatively small but of rather high efficiency. Recently, with the construction boom during the coronavirus pandemic a boosting of the demand for timber as a building material both in Germany and abroad occurred, according to the Federal Statistical Office (Destatis, 2021). But there was also oversupply during years of drought between 2018 and 2020, when especially coniferous wood from salvage logging could not be taken up by national markets. The office reports that €845 million worth of timber was exported in 2020, a total of 12.7 million cubic metres of raw timber. This was a 42.6% increase compared to the exports made in 2019, and the trend did not continue into 2021, dropping 1.5 million cubic metres, a value of only €100 million, in January and February 2021.

This case study comprises of two scenarios, both representing one side of the volatility in the forestry sector: the first models a growing forestry sector by assuming an increase in commercial forestry output representing an increased demand for construction timber and impacts on management of commercial forests; the second models a shrinking forestry sector by assuming a decrease in output, representing a reduction in demand for wood as an energy source but also increasing requirements for increasing carbon storage in forests, biodiversity and nature protection.

3.5.2 *Stakeholder engagement*

The assumptions for the scenarios to be run with the E3ME model were discussed in several meetings with stakeholders first in February 2022 and again in May and June 2023. In total about 20 stakeholders were involved in the events coming from different areas of the forestry sector in Germany, including Governmental Organisations, NGOs, industry, and forest owner representatives.

The discussion included the narratives around the scenarios, the magnitude of change in wood demand to be assumed and the policy instruments that are available and capable of steering demand. Since E3ME does not differentiate between coniferous and deciduous wood production and demand, there are certain limitations to the interpretation of results that were overcome with specific assumptions by experts on the development of the share of coniferous and deciduous wood production. Thus, we applied another that that considers this differentiation, which is essential for assessing impacts on German forestry with the national model (FABio) (discussed in D5.3. 5.3 Model run outputs from model set). The national-scale forest simulation model uses wood demand from E3ME as in input to generate scenarios of forest management within management rules. Implications

of the scenarios for net CO₂ emissions and removals from the German forestry sector are estimated with the national-scale model.

Based on the stakeholder exchange, a baseline scenario was developed. The model scenarios of higher and lower wood production, however, were developed by the modelling team in response to requests by case study leads, and were intended as “what if” scenarios, not as necessarily realistic policy scenarios (sensitivity scenarios).

3.5.3 Scenario design

This case study comprises of three scenarios, as defined by the case study leads. In addition to a baseline scenario that simulates a “business as usual” case, one scenario models a 25% increase in the output of the German forestry sector and the other models a 25% reduction in output. Both scenarios use almost identical input assumptions, with one using positive values and the other negative.

Since E3ME is demand driven rather than supply driven, we need to assume the proportion of the 25% increase in German forestry output which is consumed domestically and abroad. Of this increased forestry output, 88% is assumed to be demanded domestically, 6% demanded by the rest of the EU, and 6% by countries outside of the EU, in line with current trade data available in E3ME.

The reduction scenario uses the same methodology to create a 25% reduction in global forestry demand.

Methodological limitations

As stated above, E3ME is a demand-driven rather than supply-driven model. Due to this, the model is unable to evaluate the impact of a supply increase on trade. Instead, the trade impact must be assumed in order to create the increase in supply. In addition, exports are calculated as the inverse of the import flows, adding another level of complexity to any exogenous shocks to imports.

The analysis of the Germany case study did not include any assessment of the GHG impacts of the LMT scenarios analysed. These impacts were instead analysed using the national-scale forestry model for Germany (FABio) in the D5.3 report.

3.5.4 Modelling results

Economic impacts

The overall economic impact of these scenarios is small, with the GDP impacts peaking at 0.008% and -0.007% from the baseline in the increase and decrease scenarios respectively. Figure 15 below illustrates this GDP impact, broken down by component.

Figure 15: Components of GDP in 25% increase scenario (left) and 25% decrease scenario (right)

The consumer expenditure impacts in these scenarios are driven by the 25% increase/decrease in forestry sector employment in the respective scenarios. This change leads to a 25% increase/decrease in wages in the forestry sector, which in turn increases/decreases disposable incomes and consumer expenditure by around €400m (0.2%) compared to the baseline scenario by 2050.

The large change in imports in both scenarios are a result of the imports demanded by the forestry sector itself: since the German forestry sector is growing/shrinking in the increased/decreased production scenario, this drives higher/lower imports of forestry products demanded by the forestry sector.

Figure 16: Components of gross output in 25% increase scenario (left) and 25% decrease scenario (right)

It is important to note that the imports and exports shown in Figure 15 only account for 12% of the overall increase/decrease in output from the forestry sector. The remaining 88% is demanded by

other domestic industries, forming a part of intermediate demand rather than contributing to GDP. This is illustrated in Figure 16, showing the high proportion of gross output which is taken up by domestic demand. Figure 16 also illustrates the comparatively larger quantity of imported goods than exported goods, the imbalance of which pushes net exports negative in the 25% increase scenario (and positive in the 25% decrease scenario).

Figure 17: Global forestry trade in 25% increase scenario (left) and 25% decrease scenario (right)

Figure 17 shows the breakdown of global trade in the forestry industry. It further illustrates the high proportion of imports demanded by the German forestry industry compared to their exports. The increased and decreased exports from Germany are primarily absorbed by Austria and China, with other parts of the EU taking smaller shares. This trade breakdown is based on existing trade patterns, assuming that historical trade flows and relationships would continue regardless of the magnitude of Germany’s forestry industry. Due to the majority of Germany’s output being used domestically, the overall trade impacts are relatively small.

3.5.5 Conclusions

The modelling results suggest that only a small proportion of the assumed changes in forestry output would be demanded by foreign consumers, and as much as 88% would continue to be consumed domestically, principally by domestic industry. This results in only a net trade impact on the order of €200m, only a very small proportion of GDP.

Our modelling suggests that the net impact of higher forestry production is beneficial to the German economy, although admittedly we have not considered here the impact on competing land uses and associated economic activity. Given the built-in business case of commercial forestry as an LMT, this appears to be a relatively promising option for generating emissions reductions.

4. Conclusion

In this report, we analysed the adoption of LMT portfolios at the national scale in five case study countries: Switzerland, Sweden, the Netherlands, Canada, and Germany. In cooperation with stakeholders, we developed quantified assumptions scenarios regarding the uptake of each LMT within each national portfolio. These quantified assumptions were then entered as inputs into an E3ME modelling scenario, and the results from these scenario model runs were analysed to draw policy conclusions from the macroeconomic perspective.

The case studies analysed were diverse not only in the portfolio of LMTs selected for each country, but also in terms of the diversity of scenario elements taken into consideration, and local economic contextual details which affected assumptions. For example, some scenarios included a business case for the LMT portfolio, notably including carbon credits, but also including the sale of products linked to the LMT (such as wood products from forestry), while others did not consider the question of revenues or compensation for LMT managers. For carbon credits, different funding mechanisms were considered, including a public carbon credit system funded through either taxpayer contributions or borrowing. Some LMTs considered the impact of upscaling the LMT portfolio on alternative, competing land uses and associated economic activity: for instance, the Netherlands case study considered the impact of adopting various LMTs on the existing, nationally significant agricultural sector.

With such a diversity of case studies, it is difficult to draw overarching conclusions about the economic impacts of LMTs in general – each national context is unique, and LMT adoption will have differentiated impacts depending on where they are implemented.

However, one recurring theme is that the economic impact of land uses and economic activity displaced by upscaling LMTs can in many cases be much more significant than the economic impacts of the LMT activity itself. To a large extent, these indirect impacts depend on the local context, and on what kind of economic activity is being displaced. In some cases, these sectoral shifts could be a source of political contestation between the winners and losers of LMT adoption.

Another consideration is the business case of the LMT itself, and what are its sources of revenue. Whether LMTs are funded through taxpayer-funded government carbon credits, or borrowing-funded, can have a significant impact on overall macroeconomic results.

Even in cases where our model suggests the LMT adoption would have a negative aggregate effect on national macroeconomic outcomes, these economic impacts must be judged against the potential environmental benefits of such an intervention. Furthermore, it should be noted that while this study has assessed the economic benefits at a national level (which is understandable, given the need to convince national-level policymakers if LMT-friendly policies are to be promoted), the environmental benefits would be felt across borders.

Macroeconomic modelling with a tool such as E3ME can help us to understand the relative scale of these impacts, as well as helping us understand how these impacts can fit together. For example, the

“costs” of LMT adoption may indeed be seen as a cost by one economic agent or sector, but by the same token, these costs must be a revenue to someone else. Declines in domestic production may be replaced by increases in imports of foreign-produced goods.

The usefulness of economy, energy and environmental (E3) macroeconomic models for the task of assessing LMTs is somewhat limited if the model does not include a land-use component, as is the case with E3ME. Hence in this study, where we have made estimates of GHG emissions impacts, these have been calculated off-model, based on land-use assumptions which were used to define the LMT scenarios. A more refined model would not only be able to account for these emissions outcomes itself, but also include endogenous responses in land-use patterns in response to economic conditions and policy measures.

Our analysis is instead necessarily limited to a “what-if” analysis of LMT adoption, and the consequences of this were it to occur. All the same, understanding the scale of the impacts in these “what-if” scenario exercises create an important reference point in assessing the potential impacts of LMT adoption on their national economies and jobs.

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Annex 1: The E3ME model

1.1 Overview

E3ME is a computer-based model of the world's economic and energy systems and the environment. It was originally developed through the European Commission's research framework programmes and is now widely used in Europe and beyond for policy assessment, for forecasting and for research purposes. The global version of E3ME provides:

- better geographical coverage
- better feedbacks between individual European countries and other world economies
- better treatment of international trade with bilateral trade between regions
- new technology diffusion sub-modules

This model description provides a short summary of the E3ME model. For further details, please read the full model manual available online from www.e3me.com (Cambridge Econometrics, 2022).

1.2 Applications of E3ME

1.2.1 Scenario-based analysis

Although E3ME can be used for forecasting, the model is more commonly used for evaluating the impacts of an input shock through a scenario-based analysis. The shock may be either a change in policy, a change in economic assumptions or another change to a model variable. The analysis can be either forward looking (ex-ante) or evaluating previous developments in an ex-post manner. Scenarios may be used either to assess policy, or to assess sensitivities to key inputs (e.g. international energy prices).

For ex-ante analysis a baseline forecast up to 2050 is required; E3ME is usually calibrated to match a set of projections that are published by the European Commission and the International Energy Agency but alternative projections may be used. The scenarios represent alternative versions of the future based on a different set of inputs. By comparing the outcomes to the baseline (usually in percentage terms), the effects of the change in inputs can be determined.

1.2.2 Price or tax scenarios

Model-based scenario analyses often focus on changes in price because this is easy to quantify and represent in the model structure. Examples include:

- changes in tax rates including direct, indirect, border, energy and environment taxes
- changes in international energy prices

1.2.3 Regulatory impacts

All of the price changes above can be represented in E3ME's framework reasonably well, given the level of disaggregation available. However, it is also possible to assess the effects of regulation, albeit with an assumption about effectiveness and cost. For example, an increase in vehicle fuel-efficiency standards could be assessed in the model with an assumption about how efficient vehicles become, and the cost of these measures. This

would be entered into the model as a higher price for cars and a reduction in fuel consumption (all other things being equal). E3ME could then be used to determine:

- secondary effects, for example on fuel suppliers
- rebound effects¹³
- overall macroeconomic impacts

1.3 Comparison with CGE models and econometric specification

E3ME is often compared to Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models. In many ways the modelling approaches are similar; they are used to answer similar questions and use similar inputs and outputs. However, underlying this there are important theoretical differences between the modelling approaches.

In a typical CGE framework, optimal behaviour is assumed, output is determined by supply-side constraints and prices adjust fully so that all the available capacity is used. In E3ME the determination of output comes from a post-Keynesian framework and it is possible to have spare capacity. The model is more demand-driven and it is not assumed that prices always adjust to market clearing levels.

The differences have important practical implications, as they mean that in E3ME regulation and other policy may lead to increases in output if they are able to draw upon spare economic capacity. This is described in more detail in the model manual.

The econometric specification of E3ME gives the model a strong empirical grounding. E3ME uses a system of error correction, allowing short-term dynamic (or transition) outcomes, moving towards a long-term trend. The dynamic specification is important when considering short and medium-term analysis (e.g. up to 2020) and rebound effects¹⁴, which are included as standard in the model's results.

1.3.1 Key strengths of E3ME

In summary the key strengths of E3ME are:

- the close integration of the economy, energy systems and the environment, with two-way linkages between each component
- the detailed sectoral disaggregation in the model's classifications, allowing for the analysis of similarly detailed scenarios
- its global coverage, while still allowing for analysis at the national level for large economies
- the econometric approach, which provides a strong empirical basis for the model and means it is not reliant on some of the restrictive assumptions common to CGE models
- the econometric specification of the model, making it suitable for short and medium-term assessment, as well as longer-term trends

¹³ In the example, the higher fuel efficiency effectively reduces the cost of motoring. In the long-run this is likely to lead to an increase in demand, meaning some of the initial savings are lost. Barker et al (2009) demonstrate that this can be as high as 50% of the original reduction. (Barker, Dagoumas, & Rubin, 2009)

¹⁴ Where an initial increase in efficiency reduces demand, but this is negated in the long run as greater efficiency lowers the relative cost and increases consumption. (Barker, Dagoumas, & Rubin, 2009)

1.3.2 Limitations of the approach

As with all modelling approaches, E3ME is a simplification of reality and is based on a series of assumptions. Compared to other macroeconomic modelling approaches, the assumptions are relatively non-restrictive as most relationships are determined by the historical data in the model database. This does, however, present its own limitations, for which the model user must be aware:

- The quality of the data used in the modelling is very important. Substantial resources are put into maintaining the E3ME database and filling out gaps in the data. However, particularly in developing countries, there is some uncertainty in results due to the data used.
- Econometric approaches are also sometimes criticised for using the past to explain future trends. In cases where there is large-scale policy change, the ‘Lucas Critique’ that suggests behaviour might change is also applicable. There is no solution to this argument using any modelling approach (as no one can predict the future) but we must always be aware of the uncertainty in the model results.

The other main limitation to the E3ME approach relates to the dimensions of the model. In general, it is very difficult to go into a level of detail beyond that offered by the model classifications. This means that sub-national analysis is difficult¹⁵ and sub-sectoral analysis is also difficult. Similarly, although usually less relevant, attempting to assess impacts on a monthly or quarterly basis would not be possible.

1.4 E3ME basic structure and data

The structure of E3ME is based on the system of national accounts, with further linkages to energy demand and environmental emissions. The labour market is also covered in detail, including both voluntary and involuntary unemployment. In total there are 33 sets of econometrically estimated equations, also including the components of GDP (consumption, investment, international trade), prices, energy demand and materials demand. Each equation set is disaggregated by country and by sector.

E3ME’s historical database covers the period 1970-2018 and the model projects forward annually to 2070. The main data sources for European countries are Eurostat and the IEA, supplemented by the OECD’s STAN database and other sources where appropriate. For regions outside Europe, additional sources for data include the UN, OECD, World Bank, IMF, ILO and national statistics. Gaps in the data are estimated using customised software algorithms.

1.4.1 The main dimensions of the model

The main dimensions of E3ME are:

- 71 countries – all major world economies, the EU28 and candidate countries plus other countries’ economies grouped
- 44 or 70 (Europe) industry sectors, based on standard international classifications
- 28 or 43 (Europe) categories of household expenditure
- 25 different users of 12 different fuel types

¹⁵ If relevant, it may be possible to apply our E3-India or E3-US (currently under development) models to give state-level analysis.

- 14 types of air-borne emission (where data are available) including the 6 GHG's monitored under the Kyoto Protocol

The regions and industry sectors covered by the model are listed at the end of this document.

1.4.2 Standard outputs from the model

As a general model of the economy, based on the full structure of the national accounts, E3ME is capable of producing a broad range of economic indicators. In addition there is range of energy and environment indicators. The following list provides a summary of the most common model outputs:

- GDP and the aggregate components of GDP (household expenditure, investment, government expenditure and international trade)
- sectoral output and GVA, prices, trade and competitiveness effects
- international trade by sector, origin and destination
- consumer prices and expenditures
- sectoral employment, unemployment, sectoral wage rates and labour supply
- energy demand, by sector and by fuel, energy prices
- CO₂ emissions by sector and by fuel
- other air-borne emissions
- material demands

This list is by no means exhaustive and the delivered outputs often depend on the requirements of the specific application. In addition to the sectoral dimension mentioned in the list, all indicators are produced at the national and regional level and annually over the period up to 2050.

1.5 E3ME as an E3 model

1.5.1 The E3 interactions

Figure 18 shows how the three components (modules) of the model - energy, environment and economy - fit together. Each component is shown in its own box. Each data set has been constructed by statistical offices to conform with accounting conventions. Exogenous factors coming from outside the modelling framework are shown on the outside edge of the chart as inputs into each component. For each region's economy the exogenous factors are economic policies (including tax rates, growth in government expenditures, interest rates and exchange rates). For the energy system, the outside factors are the world oil prices and energy policy (including regulation of the energy industries). For the environment component, exogenous factors include policies such as reduction in SO₂ emissions by means of end-of-pipe filters from large combustion plants. The linkages between the components of the model are shown explicitly by the arrows that indicate which values are transmitted between components.

The economy module provides measures of economic activity and general price levels to the energy module; the energy module provides measures of emissions of the main air pollutants to the environment module, which in turn can give measures of damage to health and buildings. The energy module provides detailed price levels for energy carriers distinguished

in the economy module and the overall price of energy as well as energy use in the economy.

Figure 18: E3 linkages in the E3ME model

1.5.2 Treatment of international trade

An important part of the modelling concerns international trade. E3ME solves for detailed bilateral trade between regions (similar to a two-tier Armington model). Trade is modelled in three stages:

- econometric estimation of regions' sectoral import demand
- econometric estimation of regions' bilateral imports from each partner
- forming exports from other regions' import demands

Trade volumes are determined by a combination of economic activity indicators, relative prices and technology.

1.5.3 The labour market

Treatment of the labour market is an area that distinguishes E3ME from other macroeconomic models. E3ME includes econometric equation sets for employment, average working hours, wage rates and participation rates. The first three of these are disaggregated by economic sector while participation rates are disaggregated by gender and five-year age band.

The labour force is determined by multiplying labour market participation rates by population. Unemployment (including both voluntary and involuntary unemployment) is determined by taking the difference between the labour force and employment. This is typically a key variable of interest for policy makers.

1.5.4 The role of technology

Technological progress plays an important role in the E3ME model, affecting all three E's: economy, energy and environment. The model's endogenous technical progress indicators (TPIs), a function of R&D and gross investment, appear in nine of E3ME's econometric equation sets including trade, the labour market and prices. Investment and R&D in new technologies also appears in the E3ME's energy and material demand equations to capture energy/resource savings technologies as well as pollution abatement equipment. In addition, E3ME also captures low carbon technologies in the power, road transport, residential heating and steel sectors through the FTT sub-models (Mercure, 2012).

Main dimensions of the E3ME model

	Regions	Industries (Europe)	Industries (non-Europe)
1	Belgium	Crops, animals, etc	Agriculture etc
2	Denmark	Forestry & logging	Coal
3	Germany	Fishing	Oil & Gas etc
4	Greece	Coal	Other Mining
5	Spain	Oil and Gas	Food, Drink & Tobacco
6	France	Other mining	Textiles, Clothing & Leather
7	Ireland	Food, drink & tobacco	Wood & Paper
8	Italy	Textiles & leather	Printing & Publishing
9	Luxembourg	Wood & wood prods	Manufactured Fuels
10	Netherlands	Paper & paper prods	Pharmaceuticals
11	Austria	Printing & reproduction	Other chemicals
12	Portugal	Coke & ref petroleum	Rubber & Plastics
13	Finland	Other chemicals	Non-Metallic Minerals
14	Sweden	Pharmaceuticals	Basic Metals
15	UK	Rubber & plastic products	Metal Goods
16	Czechia	Non-metallic mineral prods	Mechanical Engineering
17	Estonia	Basic metals	Electronics
18	Cyprus	Fabricated metal prods	Electrical Engineering
19	Latvia	Computers etc	Motor Vehicles
20	Lithuania	Electrical equipment	Other Transport Equipment
21	Hungary	Other machinery/equipment	Other Manufacturing
22	Malta	Motor vehicles	Electricity
23	Poland	Other transport equip	Gas Supply
24	Slovenia	Furniture; other manufacture	Water Supply
25	Slovakia	Machinery repair/installation	Construction
26	Bulgaria	Electricity	Distribution
27	Romania	Gas, steam & air cond.	Retailing
28	Norway	Water, treatment & supply	Hotels & Catering
29	Switzerland	Sewerage & waste	Land Transport etc
30	Iceland	Construction	Water Transport
31	Croatia	Wholesale & retail MV	Air Transport
32	Turkey	Wholesale excl MV	Communications

33	Macedonia	Retail excl MV	Banking & Finance
34	USA	Land transport, pipelines	Insurance
35	Japan	Water transport	Computing Services
36	Canada	Air transport	Professional Services
37	Australia	Warehousing	Other Business Services
38	New Zealand	Postal & courier activities	Public Administration
39	Russian Fed.	Accommodation & food serv	Education
40	Rest of Annex I	Publishing activities	Health & Social Work
41	China	Motion pic, video, television	Miscellaneous Services
42	India	Telecommunications	Unallocated
43	Mexico	Computer programming etc.	
44	Brazil	Financial services	
45	Argentina	Insurance	
46	Colombia	Aux to financial services	
47	Rest Latin Am.	Real estate	
48	Korea	Imputed rents	
49	Taiwan	Legal, account, consult	
50	Indonesia	Architectural & engineering	
51	Rest of ASEAN	R&D	
52	Rest of OPEC	Advertising	
53	Rest of world	Other professional	
54	Ukraine	Rental & leasing	
55	Saudi Arabia	Employment activities	
56	Nigeria	Travel agency	
57	South Africa	Security & investigation, etc	
58	North Africa OPEC	Public admin & defence	
59	Central Africa OPEC	Education	
60	Malaysia	Human health activities	
61	Kazakhstan	Residential care	
62	Rest of North Africa	Creative, arts, recreational	
63	Rest of Central Africa	Sports activities	
64	Rest of West Africa	Membership orgs	
65	Rest of East Africa	Repair comp. & pers. goods	
66	Rest of Southern Africa	Other personal serv.	
67	Egypt	Hholds as employers	
68	Dem. Rep. of Congo	Extraterritorial orgs	
69	Kenya	Unallocated/Dwellings	
70	UAE		
71	Pakistan		

Annex 2: Scenario model inputs

2.1 Switzerland case study

2.1.1 LMT shares

LMT share assumptions were developed in consultation with the Switzerland case study lead.

Different assumptions were made for each crop/agricultural product; the shares in the table below represent additional land shares in which the LMT is adopted above baseline land shares.

	No tillage share	Organic farming share
1 Cereals	20%	20%
2 Rice	0%	10%
3 Potatoes	25%	25%
4 Other roots	15%	10%
5 Maize	15%	10%
6 Soy	15%	10%
7 Sunflower	10%	10%
8 Rapeseed	10%	10%
9 Other oil crops	10%	10%
10 Sugar crops	0%	10%
11 Poultry	0%	10%
12 Pork	0%	25%
13 Beef	0%	20%
14 Other meat & animal products	0%	0%
15 Fish	0%	0%
16 Dairy	0%	20%
17 Fruit	0%	25%
18 Vegetables	0%	30%
19 Other	0%	0%

2.1.2 Techno-economic assumptions

Levelised cost of agriculture

Scenario assumptions for LMT costs are based on a percentage increase in baseline levels of a range of production costs for each product type, including yields, fertilizer costs, machinery costs, and other production costs. Baseline data on cost components are sourced from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database maintained by the European Commission (European Commission, 2023). Cost data for Switzerland are not available, so data from Austria are used instead as a proxy.

These cost components are combined into a single “levelised cost of agriculture” (LCOA) for each product. These product LCOAs are then combined into a single LCOA for the entire agricultural sector, an average of individual product LCOAs weighted by the quantity of production – which is in turn sourced from the FAOSTAT Food Balances (FAO, 2023).

Differences in the sector-wide LCOA between the baseline and the LMT scenarios are applied as an exogenous shock to output prices for the Swiss agricultural sector – except in cases where a consumer price impact is defined, in which case this figure is used as the exogenous price shock instead.

No tillage

Production cost components for the “No tillage” LMT are assumed to be 10% higher than with tillage, based on results from a study by Ibendahl (Ibendahl, 2016). Impacts on yields are assumed to be small (Soane, et al., 2012).

	Yield	Production cost	Fertilizer cost	Machinery cost
1 Cereals	-3%	+10%	+10%	+10%
2 Rice				
3 Potatoes	-20%	+10%	+10%	+10%
4 Other roots	-20%	+10%	+10%	+10%
5 Maize	-8%	+10%	+10%	+10%
6 Soy	-3%	+10%	+10%	+10%
7 Sunflower	+2%	+10%	+10%	+10%
8 Rapeseed	+2%	+10%	+10%	+10%
9 Other oil crops	+2%	+10%	+10%	+10%
10 Sugar crops				
11 Poultry				
12 Pork				
13 Beef				
14 Other meat & animal products				
15 Fish				
16 Dairy				
17 Fruit				
18 Vegetables				
19 Other				

Organic farming

Negative impacts of organic farming techniques on yields and production costs are well-established in the literature, and are assumed to be relatively high in this scenario (Smith, et al., 2019). Meanwhile, direct price impacts for consumers are also assumed to be high (Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft, 2023).

	Yield	Production cost	Consumer price
1 Cereals	-32%	-6%	+68%
2 Rice			
3 Potatoes	-25%	-6%	+73%
4 Other roots	-25%	-6%	
5 Maize	-32%	-6%	
6 Soy	-15%	-6%	
7 Sunflower	-28%	-7%	
8 Rapeseed	-28%	-7%	
9 Other oil crops	-28%	-7%	
10 Sugar crops	-27%	-6%	
11 Poultry			+43%
12 Pork			+43%
13 Beef			+43%
14 Other meat & animal products			+43%
15 Fish			
16 Dairy			+37%
17 Fruit	-6%	3%	+48%
18 Vegetables	-23%	14%	+93%
19 Other	-27%	-7%	

2.2 Sweden case study

2.2.1 CO₂ removals

BECCS

Assumptions for potential CO₂ removals from BECCS are taken from analysis in a 2020 strategy document published by the Swedish government, “The pathway to a climate-positive future” (Statens Offentliga Utredningar, 2020, pp. 100-102). In this analysis, the potential annual CO₂ removals from BECCS are estimated to be in the range of 2-10.7 MtCO₂ by 2045.

This value is calculated from identifying the biogenic point emissions in Sweden that are larger than 0.1 MtCO₂/y, and then assessing which of these can feasibly be fitted with CCS technology by 2045, by looking at transport conditions and concentrations of CO₂ in the flue gases of the emission sources. The estimate covers all BECCS-compatible sectors such as district heating plants, paper mills, and biofuel production facilities.

For this study, we have assumed the high-end of these estimates of potential uptake of BECCS technology: 10.7 MtCO₂ annual removals by 2045. We furthermore assume a linear increase in deployment from 2026 to 2045.

We have assumed that these removals would be split across heat plants and paper/pulp sectors, according to the relative shares of biofuel use by these sectors in the E3ME baseline energy demand projections.¹⁶

Biochar

Current deployment of biochar in Sweden in 2020 is estimated based on the 2021 Biochar Market Report, where the biochar production in Europe 2020 was 17 kilotons (kt), which is equivalent to 39 ktCO₂ sequestered for at least 100 years (European Biochar Industry Consortium, 2021). In the 2022 Biochar Market Report, Scandinavia represents 23% of total biochar production (European Biochar Industry Consortium, 2022). This percentage is assumed to be the same for 2020. Sweden – being the major biochar producer in Scandinavia – was assumed to represent 75% of the Scandinavian biochar production, which would be equal to a yearly biochar production of 4.5 kt in 2020.

The production of biochar in the EU between 2010 and 2020 increased from around 2000 to 17 kt, which represents a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 24%. CAGR is the average growth rate over a period of time, and a CAGR of 24% is assumed to be the to be the maximum percentual growth rate until 2045. Similarly, the minimum and average growth rates were assumed to be 50% and 75% of the 2010-2020 CAGR respectively.

These assumptions imply deployment rates of 0.0078-0.078 MtCO₂/y. Accounting for current biochar production, this translates to a total deployment of 0.18-1.8 MtCO₂ captured annually in 2045. This can be compared to an approximation made in the Swedish government report “The path to a climate-positive future”, where the potential by 2045 was estimated at 1 MtCO₂ captured in 2045 (Statens Offentliga Utredningar, 2020).

2.2.2 Energy use

The carbon removal assumptions above imply changes in energy demand, particularly for biofuels. Figure 19 below shows the changes in energy flows that are modelled in our scenario, with the reasoning behind the assumptions explained in more detail below.

¹⁶ E3ME baseline data on biofuel consumption by sector is based on IEA World Energy Balances in the historical period and is projected forward in the baseline forecast using projections from the PRIMES 2016 reference case.

Figure 19: Energy and CO₂ emission flows in modelling approach, 2045

Note: assumptions for the district heating and paper/pulp sector shares of biofuel use are drawn from the E3ME baseline outcomes.

BECCS

The energy created by BECCS is calculated at 2.54 TWh per MtCO₂. With 10.7 MtCO₂ of CO₂ removals from BECCS assumed by 2045, this implies a total of 27.2 TWh of bioenergy being consumed annually by BECCS facilities by the same year.

Our scenario assumes that BECCS capacity additions consist of adding CCS technology to existing bioenergy-using facilities. Therefore, relative to the baseline, the additional energy use in BECCS facilities replaces bioenergy use in non-CCS bioenergy facilities, keeping final energy consumption (from buildings and industry) unchanged. This reduces the use of biofuels without CCS by 27.2 TWh.

However, additional energy is required to power the CCS technology itself, also known as the “energy penalty” for CCS technology. This additional energy required for CCS is calculated at 0.3 TWh per MtCO₂, leading to an additional 3.21 TWh of bioenergy consumed annually by 2045. We assume this is shared between the paper & pulp sector and heat plants, using the same approach as for CO₂ removal assumptions.

Biochar

The energy demanded by the biochar process is calculated at 5.4 TWh per MtCO₂. With 1.8 MtCO₂ of carbon removals from biochar assumed by 2045, this implies an additional 9.72 TWh of biofuels being used in these processes.

The biochar production process generates excess heat energy as a byproduct. As with BECCS energy use, final demand of heat energy (from buildings and industrial sectors) is assumed to be unchanged, and therefore this supply of excess heat energy is assumed to displace existing production of (bioenergy-based) heat energy by the district heating sector.

Since the biochar process produces 3 TWh excess heat per MtCO₂ captured, and again using the assumption of 1.8 MtCO₂ captured by 2045, this results in 5.4 TWh excess heat produced in the biochar production process. This therefore displaces an equivalent amount of heat production from the district heating sector. This displaced heat production is assumed to use conventional biofuel technologies (without CCS), so ultimately this implies a displacement of 5.4 TWh of biofuel use by the district heating sector.

2.2.3 Techno-economic assumptions

BECCS

Capital expenditure (CAPEX) costs of BECCS are estimated to be SEK 400-600 per tCO₂ for the actual facility.¹⁷ Operating expenditure costs (OPEX) are estimated at 150-300 SEK/tCO₂ for transport of CO₂ to a storage site, and 100-200 SEK/tCO₂ for the storage (Statens Offentliga Utredningar, 2020). The upper ends of these ranges were assumed, leading to CAPEX and OPEX cost estimates of €56/tCO₂ and €47/tCO₂, respectively.¹⁸

Total annual CAPEX expenditure is assumed to be proportional to capacity *additions*, rather than levels. That is, if CO₂ removals increase linearly by 1 MtCO₂ each year, and CAPEX costs are €1/tCO₂, then annual investment expenditures will remain static at €1m per year. Since investment takes place throughout the scenario period (rather than being concentrated in year 1), no discount rate is applied to investment costs.

Biochar

CAPEX costs for biochar production is assumed to be €90/tCO₂. This is based on a CAPEX span of €77.5 to €106 found in a techno-economic analysis (Haeldermans, et al., 2020). OPEX is assumed to be 10% of CAPEX.

¹⁷ Capital investment costs are assumed to be fixed (in real terms) throughout the scenario period, with no returns to scale. Financing is assumed to be available for any capital expenditures, meaning no crowding out of private investment is assumed.

¹⁸ An exchange rate of 10.64 EUR per SEK is assumed, based on World Bank official exchange rates in 2022 (World Bank, 2023).

2.2.4 Carbon prices

CO₂ prices are assumed to follow projections of the EU ETS price from the PRIMES 2016 Reference Case.

The carbon price for biochar is modelled as double that of BECCS, per the historical ratio between the CORC Carbon Removal Price Indexes for biochar (CORCCHAR) and general carbon removals (CORCX) (Puro.earth, 2023).

2.3 Netherlands case study

2.3.1 Land use

Our assumptions for economic and energy system impacts of LMT implementation described in the following section begin with assumptions regarding the uptake of those LMTs in the Netherlands, in terms of quantities of land affected.

In general, each LMT is assumed to be adopted on a certain share of a particular land type. For instance, we have assumed that 40% of peatland is rewetted and converted to paludiculture methods.

These LMT land shares are applied to existing estimates of current land use in the Netherlands, which sourced from FAOSTAT. Outside of the assumed conversion of the stated land types to LMTs, current land use shares are assumed to be static over time until the end of the scenario period.

The FAOSTAT land use data includes both agricultural land and pastureland as categories, but not peatland. To address this, we used a separate estimate of peatland area in the Netherlands of 290,000 ha. For simplicity we also assumed this peatland is entirely contained within (and we therefore subtracted this area from) the pastureland category in the FAOSTAT dataset.¹⁹

Table 2: Scenario assumptions for LMT adoption by land use type

LMT	Land type converted	Share of land type area converted
Paludiculture	Peatland	40%
Afforestation	Agricultural land	10%
	Pastureland	10%
Agroforestry	Agricultural land	25%
Anaerobic digestion of manure	Pastureland	25%

2.3.2 Energy

a. Manure anaerobic digestion

Anaerobic digestion of manure produces biogas as a byproduct, which we assumed is then consumed in bioenergy with CCS (BECCS) power plants.

The quantity of biogas produced is estimated based on biogas coefficients applied to the total population of cattle in the Netherlands. Differential emissions assumptions are developed for dairy and non-dairy cows. Each dairy cow is assumed to produce sufficient manure for 500 Nm³ of biogas per year, while other cattle are assumed to produce 100 Nm³ per year.²⁰

These per-head biogas production coefficients are then multiplied by population of each category of cattle: 2.5 million dairy, and 1.2 million other cattle.²¹

¹⁹ <https://www.recare-hub.eu/case-studies/veenweidegebied-the-netherlands>

²⁰ https://iea-etsap.org/E-TechDS/PDF/P11_BiogasProd_ML_Dec2013_GSOK.pdf

²¹ <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/cijfers/detail/84952NED#>

2.3.3 Emissions

a. Paludiculture

A simple assumption is used for annual CO₂ removals from paludiculture. Removals are assumed to be proportional to the total land area of rewetted peatland, with a total 8.1 tCO₂ annual removals assumed per hectare of rewetted peatland.

b. Afforestation and agroforestry

For the afforestation and agroforestry LMTs, annual CO₂ removal assumptions are calculated on the basis of an age-based sequestration calculation. CO₂ sequestration is assumed to be associated with growth of newly planted forest, but net emissions associated with this land use are assumed to fall back to zero as the tree reaches maturity. For each *additional* hectare of forest added in a given year, an age-based profile of annual CO₂ removals is assumed for the following 50 years.

For afforestation, removals are assumed to amount to 4.6 tCO₂ per ha annually in the first 10 years after plantation, and 9.1 tCO₂ per ha annually in the following 40 years. For agroforestry, these assumptions are halved, with 2.3 tCO₂ per ha removed in the first 10 years, and 4.6 tCO₂ per ha in the following 40 years.

c. Anaerobic digestion of manure

Anaerobic manure digestion processes result in prevented emissions of methane (CH₄), a greenhouse gas, from animal manure. Our assumptions for prevented emissions are based on an estimate of manure CH₄ emissions per cow per year, multiplied by the cow population in the Netherlands.

Differential emissions assumptions are developed for dairy and non-dairy cows: 34 kgCO₂ per head per year for dairy cows, and 10 kgCO₂ per head per year for other cattle.²² These per-head emissions are then apportioned according to the population of each category of cattle in the Netherlands (see previous section on energy production).

On the 35% of pastureland on which anaerobic manure digestion is applied by 2050 (see previous section), half of these CH₄ emissions are assumed to be prevented. This leads to a total of 17 ktCH₄ (or 0.475 MtCO₂e)²³ prevented annually by 2050.

2.3.4 Economic

a. LMT implementation costs

CAPEX and OPEX costs for each LMT were developed based on assumptions listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Capital and operating expenditure assumptions by LMT

LMT	Variable	Value	Source
Paludiculture	CAPEX	€2,363/ha	Ramsar 2021 ²⁴

²² https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/pdf/4_Volume4/V4_10_Ch10_Livestock.pdf

²³ Based on global warming potentials from the AR5 report:

https://ghgprotocol.org/sites/default/files/ghgp/Global-Warming-Potential-Values%20%28Feb%2016%202016%29_1.pdf

²⁴

https://www.ramsar.org/sites/default/files/documents/library/strp24_313c_peatland_restoration_tr_e.pdf

	OPEX	€332 per ha	Wageningen Economic Research 2020 ²⁵
Afforestation	CAPEX	€52,000/ha land purchase €13,750/ha planting costs	Stichting Nationale Kostofmarkt 2021 ²⁶ , Table 1, pp.38-39
Agroforestry	CAPEX	€6,875/ha planting costs	50% of afforestation planting costs (i.e. half as many trees planted)
Manure anaerobic digestion	CAPEX	\$11,000 / Nm ³ / hour	IEA ESTAP 2013 ²⁷
	OPEX	10% of CAPEX	n/a

N.B.: No OPEX cost assumptions were developed for afforestation and agroforestry LMTs.

Implementation cost assumptions for paludiculture, afforestation and agroforestry are denominated on a per-hectare basis, so total costs are calculated based so are applied to the land use calculations described in section 1 above. For manure anaerobic digestion, where cost assumptions are denominated per unit of energy produced, total costs are calculated based on energy production assumptions described in section 2 above.

b. Avoided subsidence costs from peatland rewetting

Degraded peatland in the Netherlands is associated with significant and increasing costs due to soil subsidence, including damage to buildings, increased water management costs, and costs to infrastructure. Aside from environmental benefit, rewetting these peatlands (through the paludiculture LMT) would bring the added benefit of avoiding these subsidence costs. Therefore, our LMT scenario included assumptions regarding avoided costs to firms and consumers from the avoided impacts of future subsidence, relative to the baseline.

The cumulative costs of reconstructing damaged buildings and infrastructure over the 2010-2050 period were assumed to be €16 billion for urban areas, €5.2 billion for urban infrastructure, and €1 billion for rural buildings and infrastructure.²⁸ For urban buildings, 60% of costs were allocated to consumer expenditure on maintenance and repair, and 40% to firms' capital expenditure, with a stronger weighting of firms' costs to services sectors. For rural areas, the equivalent split was assumed to be 70% to 30%, with a stronger weighting of firms' costs to the agricultural sector. Urban infrastructure costs were assumed to be borne by public investment.

Cumulative avoided water management costs were assumed to be €200 million, and were allocated to unit costs of the water supply sector, pushing up the price of water.

²⁵ https://www.rli.nl/sites/default/files/rapport_vernatting_groene_hart_kostprijs_melk_en_co2-prijs_-_wageningen_ur.pdf

²⁶ <https://nationaleco2markt.nl/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/210603-Methode-Aanleg-bos-en-beplanting-buiten-bosverband.pdf>

²⁷ https://iea-etsap.org/E-TechDS/PDF/P11_BiogasProd_ML_Dec2013_GSOK.pdf

²⁸ https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/Subsiding_soils_rising_costs_Findings.pdf

c. Trade effects from reduced agricultural output

Agricultural output is assumed to be reduced as a result of conversion of agricultural area to other land uses. Real-terms agricultural gross output was assumed to be reduced proportionally to the share of land affected. This reduction in output was assumed to be borne by a loss of agricultural exports, which directly impacts GDP outcomes.

2.4 Canada case study

2.4.1 Oil and bitumen extraction

Data on total oil extraction between 1985 and 2016 are taken from Statistics Canada's 'Crude oil and equivalent, monthly supply and disposition (x1,000)' (Statistics Canada, 2023). Data for the period 2016 – 2022 are from Statistics Canada's 'Supply and disposition of crude oil and equivalent' (Statistics Canada, 2023), with 2022 being excluded due to incomplete data.

Historical data on bitumen production between 1986 and 2021 are taken from Oil Sands Magazine's 'Oil Sands Operations: Bitumen Production' data (Oil Sands Magazine, 2023), and post-2016 data are calculated from Statistics Canada's 'Supply and disposition of crude oil and equivalent' (Table 25-10-0063-01) as the sum of processed crude bitumen and non-upgraded crude bitumen. The growth rate of this data is used to estimate the pre-1985 data for total bitumen extraction. This total is then split between 'Mined' and 'In-Situ' extraction using the ratio provided in the Oil Sands Magazine dataset. Only the ratio of pre-2016 data is used for a more reliable split.

The projected extraction rate for oil is taken from the Canada Energy Regulator's (CER) Canada's Energy Future 2021 Evolving Policies Scenario, and the growth rate of this projection is used to estimate a projection for bitumen extraction after 2021.

2.4.2 Land use

The total land used in the restoration efforts is estimated from the total oil extraction and the land use per unit of oil produced estimated by Drever et al. (2021, Figure 7). It is assumed that all plots of land contain an equal share of the total cumulative oil extracted, and it is assumed that each plot of land is worked at full capacity until either the plot is depleted of its oil reserves, or the total oil extracted that year is reached. This leads to plots becoming degraded steadily. Since the plots available for restoration are assumed to increase linearly across the modelled period, the cumulative total is interpolated quadratically to estimate the land available for restoration at any given point in the modelled period, starting from no land available in 2021.

Mined extraction sites are assumed to have an 80 year lifetime (Natural Resources Canada, 2015). In situ extraction sites are assumed to have a 25 year lifespan (Edmunds, 2010).

2.4.3 Emissions

It is assumed that of the land cleared for oil extraction, 50% is peatland and 50% is forested. As such, the CO₂ emissions are calculated to take both into account, as displayed in Figures 5 and 6 below.

Figures 20 and 6: GHG emissions by land type in degraded and restored states

The emissions associated with peatland degradation and restoration are taken from Drever et al. (2021, Supplementary materials, p38) and the emissions associated with deforestation are taken from Kurz et al. 2013 (p271). They calculate the cumulative area of deforestation as 674 kha over the period 1990–2008, and calculate the average annual emissions (both direct and residual) as 6.2 Tg CO₂e year⁻¹.

2.4.4 Industry costs

The base cost of restoration is calculated by Drever et al (2021, Supplementary Info (SI), page 38) as between 3500–4000/ha, giving an average cost of 3750 CAD/ha. It is assumed that these reclamation costs are not evenly distributed across the lifespan of the plot instead being disproportionately weighted towards the beginning of the reclamation process. As such, it is assumed that reclamation costs fall by 30% in years 5–10 of the plot being worked and 50% from year 11 onwards once the reclamation of the plot is fully established.

The cost of monitoring the reclamation project is estimated at 89.6 CAD/ha, an assumption provided by stakeholders. It is estimated that 63,000 CAD will be spent in year 0 on EO tool development, followed by 50,000 CAD spent in year 1 on an ALCES customisation model and a subsequent annual subscription for that model until year 10 (priced at 5,000 CAD pa). Salaries associated with the reclamation are estimated at 170,000 CAD pa starting in year 1, covering one project manager and one full time researcher. These costs reduce to 100,000 CAD pa in year 5 when it is assumed that the researcher is no longer required. The salary is averaged over years 5 to 10 to account for inflation and rises to 130,000 CAD in years 11 through 20 for the same reason. 20% contingency is added to overall costs.